

ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECT OF SOME NIGERIAN MEDICINAL PLANTS ON DRUG- RESISTANT SALMONELLA SPECIES ISOLATED FROM ENVIROMENTAL SOURCES

Oluyeye, J.O., Olaleye, A.J and Oluyeye, A.O.

Department of Microbiology, University of Ado Ekiti, Nigeria P.M.B. 5363 Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State.

ABSTRACT

Sensitivity of *Salmonella* species isolated from different environmental sources to the extracts of *Azadirachita indica*, *Psidium guajava*, *Kigelia africana* and *Aloe microcarpa* was investigated. Susceptibility of the isolates to amoxicillin, ofloxacin, tetracycline, gentamicin, nalixidic acid, nitrofurantoin and cotrimoxazole was also examined. The sensitivity assay was done using agar dilution technique at concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 20% v/v. The concentration of all the extracts of the experimental plants that inhibited the growth of *Salmonella* species ranged from 10 to 20% v/v with minimum inhibitory concentration of 5.0% v/v. All the extracts at concentration of 20%v/v exhibited 100% growth inhibition on *Salmonella* isolates. All the isolates exhibited resistance patterns ranging from 50 to 100% against the antibiotics examined. Anti-nutrients constituents detected in all the plants materials were alkaloids (1.29-3.57%), tannins (4.69-6.33%), saponins (2.45-7.57%), phenols (0.26-0.60%) and Flavonoids 0.41-1.00%. The need to source for anti-typhoidal drugs from medicinal plants is discussed.

KEYWORDS: *Salmonella* infection, isolates, *Azadirachita indica*, *Psidium guajava*, *Kigelia africana* and *Aloe microcarpa*

INTRODUCTION

Salmonella infection is one of the most common food-borne infections worldwide (Santos *et al.*, 2003). In the United States, an estimated 1.4 million cases and more than 500 human deaths occur annually, and are even more detrimental in the developing world (Mead *et al.*, 1999, Santos *et al.*, 2003). An estimated incidence of 33 million cases of typhoidal Salmonellosis occur in developing countries of Africa and Southeast Asia (Iwanoff, 1999; Sood *et al.*, 1999). Worldwide, there are an estimated 20 million and 700,000 deaths annually due to typhoid illness constituting a major health problem in developing countries. (Kumar *et al.*, 2009). The persisting morbidity of *Salmonella* especially *S. typhi* may be attributed to the increasing resistance rate of this pathogen to a number of commonly used antimicrobial compounds (Helms *et al.*, 2005).

The efficacies of first line antibiotics such as chloramphenicol and cot-trimoxazole and third generation cephalosporins have been doubtful following the emergence of multi-drug resistance in *Salmonella* (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2000; 2007). This situation necessitates the need to exploit more herbal remedies as a supplement to orthodox treatment of typhoid cases, and a continuous search for antimicrobial metabolites not only from microorganisms but also from higher plants and to exploit herbal remedies as a supplement to orthodox treatment of infectious diseases.

Traditional medical practitioners in Nigeria use a variety of herbal preparations for treatment of different kinds of ailment which include many microbial infections such as sore throat gonorrhoea, diarrhoea and typhoid fever (Nwanna *et al.*, 2005). *Kigelia africana* which is one the experimental plants used in this study occurs throughout tropical Africa and it belongs to the family Bignoniaceae. The decoction of the leaves and stem bark of the plant is usually recommended for malaria fever, typhoid fever, kidney disorder and dysentery (Del-Hoyo, 1997).

The aim of this study therefore was to investigate the antibacterial activity of *Azadirachta indica*, *Kigelia Africana*, *Psidium guajava* and *Aloe microcarpa* on antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* species isolated from environmental sources

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of plant materials:

The stem barks of *Psidium guajava* , *Aloe microcarpa* , *Kigelia Africana* and *Azadirachta indica* were collected from Ado Ekiti community in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The plant materials were processed by air drying for 8 weeks and then ground into powder. The voucher specimen was deposited to the Herbarium Unit of the Department of Plant Science, University of Ado Ekiti, Nigeria after identification.

Isolation of Salmonella species for bio-assay:

Salmonella species were isolated from poultry droppings, cow dung and domestic waste effluents. The isolation was done by streaking the Buffered Peptone Water (BPW) suspension of the specimen collected from the various sources on Shigella-Salmonella (SS) agar plates and incubated at 37° C. The colonies that were developed were purified on SS-agar and Nutrient agar plates. The Salmonella isolates were identified using biochemical tests as described by Barrow and Feltham (1993) serotyping was done using a commercially prepared agglutinating kit (Oxoid, Basingstoke England). The pure culture of Salmonella isolates were kept on slant and refrigerated at 12° C until used for the bio-assay of the plant extracts.

Extraction procedures of the plant materials:

Thirty gramme of air-dried macerate of plant materials are separately suspended in 120 ml of 10% chloroform-water, ethanol and ethyl acetate in 250 ml sized conical flasks. The extractions of the plant materials were allowed for a period of 5 days at 28°C ± 1°C. The extracts were filtered using Watman filter paper No 1 and evaporated to dryness. The residues were reconstituted with 20% glycerol to make a stock concentration of 100 mg/ml. Sterilization of the extracts was done using membrane filter. The extracts were refrigerated at 12° C until used for bio-assay.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

Susceptibility test of the enteric bacterial isolates were carried out against seven antibiotics which comprised amoxycillin (amx) 25µg, cotrimoxazole (cot) 25µg, nitrofurantoin (nit) 300µg, gentamicin (gen) 10µg, nalidixic acid (nal) 300µg, ofloxacin (ofl) 30µg and tetracycline (tet) 30µg.. Standardized bacterial inoculums i. e 1 to 2 X10⁷ cfu/ml with 0.5 McFarland standard was introduced to the surface of Diagnostic Sensitivity Test agar (DST). The surfaces of the agar were allowed to dry and the multi discs of antibiotic were aseptically placed on the plates and allowed to diffuse for 30 minutes. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 18hrs. Diameter of clear zone of incubation were measured and recorded. The data were analyzed according to (NCCLS, 2002).

Antimicrobial assay of the extracts:

Antimicrobial assay of the extracts was performed on 78 isolates of *Salmonella* species from different environmental sources using agar dilution method. The extracts were added to the molten sensitivity test agar to make final concentration of 0.5%, 1.0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% v/v. The agar extract mixtures were allowed to set. The test organisms were standardized according to method described by Bauer *et al.* (1966).The standardized inocula were radially streaked on the agar-extract mixture plates and then incubated at 37° C for 18 hours. The plates were observed for growth inhibition and the numbers of *Salmonella* isolates that were inhibited at the different concentration of the extracts were recorded.

Qualitative determination of phytochemical constituents of the extracts:

The profile of the medicinal plants screened in this study are presented in Table 1. The screening procedures were adapted from the work of Sofowora, (1993) and Harbourne, (1973). Quantitative analysis for tannin was carried out as described by Van-Burden and Robinson (1981), phenols by spectrophotometric method,, saponins (Obadoni and Ochuko, (2001) flavonoids, (Boham and Kocipai-Abyazan, 1971) and alkaloids (Harborne, (1973)

RESULTS

All the isolates of Salmonella used in this study exhibited resistance patterns ranging from 50 to 100% against the antibiotics examined (Figure 1).The extracts of *Azadirachta indica*, *Psidium guajava*, *Kigelia Africana* and *Aloe microcarpa* were observed to possess antibacterial activity on strains of these antibiotic resistant Salmonella isolated from different environmental sources (Table 2). At the concentrations ranging from 0.5% to 5.0 (v/v) less than 4%

growth inhibition was observed. *Azadirachta indica* at concentration of 10% exhibited growth inhibition on *Salmonella* species in range of 17%-37% while at the concentrations of 15% and 20% (v/v), complete growth inhibition of the test organism was achieved (Table 2). Growth inhibition achieved by extracts of *Psidium guajava* at the concentrations of 10% ranged from 3% to 23% and at the concentration of 15% and 20% (v/v), growth inhibition of *Salmonella* was between 80% and 100%. This was also the case for the extracts of *Kigelia africana* except that ethyl acetate extract of the plant at concentration of 10% to 20% exhibited 100% inhibition of the test organism. The same pattern of activity was recorded for the extracts of *Aloe microcarpha* except that ethyl acetate was not an effective solvent for the extraction of the plant. Anti-nutrients constituents detected in all the plants materials were alkaloids (1.29-3.57%), tannins (4.69-6.33%), saponins (2.45-7.57%), phenols (0.26-0.60%) and Flavonoids 0.41-1.00% (Table 3)

DISCUSSION

The results in this study revealed the antibacterial potential of the extracts of the experimental plants: *Azadirachta indica*, *Psidium guajava*, *Kigelia africana* and *Aloe microcarpha* on antibiotic-resistant strains of *Salmonella*. Antibiotic and multiresistance of *Salmonella* spp. have increased a great deal due to the indiscriminate use of antibiotics, and this necessitates the need to search for alternative drugs from plant sources. Although the antibacterial effect of some of these medicinal plants has been proven in earlier studies (Houghton, *et al.*, 2002; Grace *et al.*, 2002, Subramaniam *et al.*, 2005), however, the findings in this study highlights their potential in combating the menace of antibiotic resistant strains of pathogenic bacteria of medical importance. Earlier studies have identified that Azadirachtin the active component of Neem is of the phenol group (Subramaniam *et al.*, 2005). The antibacterial action of *Azadirachta indica* is mainly due to the inhibition of cell membrane synthesis (Singh *et al.*, 1990).

This is not surprising in that the secondary metabolites of higher plant origin such as alkaloids, phenols and flavonoids have been suggested to possess antibacterial properties (Aboaba and Efuwape 2001; Goud *et al.*, 2008). Alkaloids, tannins, saponins were detected in considerable higher concentrations than phenols and flavonoids in the extracts of all the experimental plant (Table 3). Hence, the antimicrobial activity of these plants can be attributed by the presence of alkaloids, tannins and saponins. It has been well reported that alkaloids, phenols are plant metabolites well known for antimicrobial activity (Goud *et al.*, 2008) and these phytochemicals exert their antimicrobial activity through different mechanisms. It is noteworthy that the first generations of plant drugs were usually simple botanicals employed in more or less crude form. Several effective medicine are used in their natural state such as *Cinchona*, *Opium*, *Belladonna* and *Aloe* were selected as therapeutic agents based on empirical evidence of their clinical application by traditional societies from different parts of the world. Following the industrial revolution, a second generation of plant based drugs emerged based on scientific processing of the plant extracts to isolate "their active constituents" (Maurice *et al.*, 2007).

The second generation phytopharmaceutical agents were pure molecules and some of the compounds were even more pharmacologically active than their synthetic counterparts. Notable examples were quinine from *Conchona*, reserpine from *Rauwolfia*, and more recently taxol from *Taxus* species. These compounds differed from the synthetic therapeutic agents only to their origin. They followed the same method of development and evaluation as other pharmaceutical agents.

The result of this study suggests that these experimental medicinal plants contain appreciable amounts of anti-nutrients which can provide an alternative solution for the treatment of infections caused by antibiotic resistant *Salmonella* species.

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Table 1: Profile of medicinal plants used

Medicinal plant	Common name	Parts used	Medicinal uses	References
<i>Kigelia africana</i>	Sausage tree	Leaves/Stem bark	Dermal complaints, Sore throat, gonorrhea, diarrhea, typhoid fever	Nwanna <i>et al.</i> , 2005 McBurnet <i>et al.</i> , 2004
<i>Azadiractha indica</i>	Neem	Leaves, root, Stem bark	Malaria, skin diseases, jaundice, liver disorder, antipyretic	Collins <i>et al.</i> , 1995
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Guava		Sore throat, colic diarrhea, cough and cold	Mauna <i>et al.</i> , 2000 Ebama <i>et al.</i> , 1991

Figure 1: Antibiotic resistance patterns of Salmonella species isolated from environmental sources

Table 2: Sensitivity pattern of Salmonella species to some Nigerian medicinal plants.

Extract concentration (%)	Sensitivity pattern (%)											
	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>			<i>Psidium guajava</i>			<i>Kigelia africana</i>			<i>Aloe microcarpa</i>		
	AET	ETA	EAE	AET	ETA	EAE	AET	ETA	EAE	AET	ETA	EAE
0.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5.0	0	0	0	1.0	0	3.0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10.0	17.0	34.0	37.0	23.0	3.0	6.0	9.0	17.0	100.0	25.0	35.0	0
15.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	80.0	100.0	100.0	80.0	74.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	11.0
20.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Aqueous extract (AET), Ethanolic extract (ETA), Ethyl acetate extract (EAE)

Table 3: Anti-nutrient constituents of the experimental plant materials

Plant materials	Phytochemical constituents (%)				
	Alkaloids	Tannin	Saponins	Phenol	Flavonoids
<i>Aloe microcarpa</i>	2.35	6.33	7.57	0.26	0.66
<i>Kigelia africana</i>	3.57	5.12	2.45	0.43	0.55
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	1.29	4.69	4.85	0.60	1.00
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	2.49	5.55	3.74	0.34	0.41

Received for Publication: 05/02/10

Accepted for Publication: 02/04/10

Corresponding Author

Oluyeye, J.O.,

Department of Microbiology, University of Ado Ekiti, Nigeria P.M.B. 5363 Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State.

Email: kemioluyeye@yahoo.com